

THE PROBLEMS OF ARTISTRY IN THE FANTASTIC PROSE OF A. SVISTUNOV.

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Abstract: The article deals with the problems of logical consistency, character development, the use of metaphors and symbolism, style and language, as well as social relevance. Through a literature review and analysis of key aspects of fantasy literature, the article offers insights into these problems and possible approaches to overcoming them.

Keywords: fiction literature, fictionality, logical consistency, character development, metaphors, symbolism, style, language

Fantasy literature, as a genre, offers us a world of possibilities where reality and fantasy intertwine. However, despite its popularity and wide readership, fiction also faces a number of problems of artistry that can affect the quality and reception of works. In this article, we will look at several key problems of fiction literature and their impact on the genre.

One of the key problems in fantasy literature is the need to establish a logical sequence in the story and world created by the author. In fantasy worlds where supernatural forces operate or the normal laws of physics are violated, the author needs to build an internal logic that is understandable and convincing to the reader. A lack of logical consistency can lead to a loss of engagement and credibility on the part of the reader.

Creating compelling characters in fantasy literature is another challenge. Readers should be able to empathise and understand the characters, no matter how fantastic the world they are in. However, sometimes authors tend to neglect character development in favour of exploring fantastic ideas and concepts. This

can lead to superficial or unrealistic representations of the characters, which negatively affects the artistry of the work.

Metaphors and symbols are important tools of fiction in any literary work, including fantasy literature. However, some authors may use metaphors and symbols inconsistently or vaguely, which may reduce the effectiveness of their impact on the reader. Fiction literature that successfully uses metaphors and symbols helps to create deep meaning and emotional resonance, which is one of the main criteria for artistic quality.

Fiction, like any other genre, requires attention to style and language. The use of original and colourful descriptions, rich vocabulary and artistic figures of speech contribute to the atmosphere and depth of the work. However, sometimes authors can get carried away with technical details or excessive specificity of the fantasy world, which can lead to unnecessary complexity or fatigue the reader.

Although fantasy literature often presents worlds and events far removed from reality, it can also serve as a vehicle for addressing social issues and challenging thoughts about contemporary society. The problem is that some authors may focus more on creating a fantasy world, missing the opportunity to address current social issues. In such cases, the artistry of the work suffers from a lack of connection to the real world and its problems.

Issues of artistry in fantasy literature play an important role in determining the quality and effectiveness of works. Logical consistency, character development, use of metaphors and symbolism, style and language, and social relevance all influence whether a work is artistically significant. Authors and readers of fiction literature should pay attention to these problems and strive to overcome them in order to create deeper, more compelling and socially relevant works in this amazing genre.

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